

GraspOS Infrastructure: Enhancing Discoverability of Open Resources for Responsible Research Assessment

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Background and Purpose

Research assessment is the field related to the evaluation of research activities, outputs, practices, actors, and roles across various dimensions such as quality, novelty, impact, usage, and openness. This includes the process of supporting researchers in their career progression, evaluating research performed by Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and measuring the scientific, societal, and economic impact of research grants for Research Funding Organisations (RFOs).

Current research assessment practices face significant challenges, including the misuse and misinterpretation of non-transparent quantitative indicators, the reliance on proprietary data sources, and an overemphasis on publications while neglecting other valuable contributions to research. There is an increasing recognition of the need for a more responsible approach to assessing research and researchers. Such an approach should (a) consider the values, scope, and context of each assessment event, (b) integrate qualitative evidence alongside well-supported quantitative data and indicators, and (c) recognize the diverse roles and contributions of research work, ensuring all efforts are appropriately acknowledged. Additionally, it should promote transparency in the assessment process by prioritizing the use of open scholarly data sources, fostering trust and inclusivity in research evaluation practices. Finally, since openness in science is widely recognized due to its effect in research credibility and knowledge sharing, there is a need for frameworks and technologies that will enable responsible research assessment that takes into consideration efforts related to Open Science to encourage and reward the adoption of OS practices from researchers and RPOs.

In this talk, we present the GraspOS infrastructure (<https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/>), an open infrastructure that aims to alleviate the aforementioned problems by aggregating and making discoverable open resources (data, tools, services, templates, and guidance materials) that can catalyse the implementation of necessary reforms in existing research assessment frameworks. The infrastructure is a key exploitable output of the GraspOS project (<https://graspos.eu/>), a Horizon Europe project with the objective to enhance the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem with components to pave the way towards Open-Science-aware, Responsible Research Assessment.

The GraspOS Infrastructure Architecture

The aim of the GraspOS Infrastructure is to enable the discovery and access of responsible research assessment resources from the end-users and to facilitate the work of tool and

service developers in consuming (meta)data assets from a set of supported, federated scholarly (meta)data sources.

To support this purpose, the GraspOS Infrastructure adopts an architecture consisting of a series of core catalogues that facilitate the discovery of research assessment resources, a Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL) that improves interoperability of the federated data sources, and a Web-based front-end that acts like the entry point to the infrastructure informing the end-users about the contents and assisting them in identifying federated resources of interest. The catalogues are designed in a way to collect rich metadata that are useful to facilitate the discoverability of the respective resources in the EOSC ecosystem. More details about each core component and its implementation are provided in next sections.

Data Catalogue

This component enables users to discover, understand, and search for data assets within the GraspOS infrastructure. The datasets registered in the GraspOS Data Catalogue include raw or structured data that can be used to either directly support the conduction of Open-Science-aware responsible research assessment events or produce indicators, track records, narratives or other evidence that could be valuable in such processes. The Data Catalogue aggregates metadata and access information for all datasets and data sources federated within the GraspOS system. More specifically, apart from a set of basic metadata related to each dataset (e.g., its title, owners, licence), the GraspOS Data Catalogue also contains information about the location of the respective GraspOS API deployment, enabling the programmatic access to the data source contents.

Tools Catalogue

This component aims to facilitate the discovery of GraspOS tools by collecting their metadata offering also an integration with EOSC. The tools registered in the GraspOS Tools catalogue are stand-alone pieces of software, such as scripts, executables, libraries, or even workflows, which can be used by installing and executing them locally on a computer or computational cluster owned by the end-user to conduct a particular type of analysis and/or produce data in the context of research assessment events or related processes.

Services Catalogue

The aim of this component is to facilitate the discovery of GraspOS services by collecting and indexing their metadata. The services collected in the GraspOS Services Catalogue are pieces of software that provide a set of functions or features for the end user, which can be helpful in the context of research assessment processes and that are typically hosted on a remote server or cluster and accessed via a Web interface or API. Essentially, the service providers aim to offer them in a 24/7 manner giving guarantees for the respective Quality of Service (QoS), such as the service availability. The GraspOS Services Catalogue is also expected to facilitate the integration of the previous services into the EOSC ecosystem. It essentially provides GraspOS end-users with a centralized and intuitive platform to explore and access the various services offered and it is based on the OpenAIRE Catalogue open-source software.

Assessment Process Resources Catalogue

The aim of this component is to facilitate the discovery of resources facilitating the assessment process, such as:

- templates for documents, which can be used during the research assessment process, such as templates for documenting the assessment readiness, stakeholder mapping, value and/or purpose statement of the respective research assessment events, or similar resources.
- guidance documents, which can inform readers on subjects related to responsible and Open-Science-aware research assessment.
- checklists, which are systematic list of steps arranged in a specific order, used as a tool to ensure that all necessary actions for research assessment processes are taken and nothing is overlooked
- indicator toolboxes, which are comprehensive collections of metrics and indicators designed to estimate various aspects of research performance, impact, and quality

Data Interoperability and Access Layer

The GraspOS infrastructure contains a “Data Interoperability and Access Layer” (called “DIAL” for brevity) which aims to facilitate the integration and harmonisation of (meta)data from various sources and formats within the infrastructure. This aims to ease the work of developers in implementing tools and added-value services on top of the respective data sources.

The GraspOS DIAL essentially comprises the union of all the API endpoints that offer access to the contents of the (federated) data sources included in the GraspOS infrastructure. All data sources included to the GraspOS infrastructure should offer API endpoints which are compatible (and interoperable) with each other. To this end, GraspOS is building upon the guidelines and specifications of widely accepted standards. More specifically, the API is based on the “Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework” (SKG-IF) delivered by a working group of Research Data Alliance (RDA).

Web-based Front-end

This component is a front-end user interface (UI) that can be used by the end-users to help them search for the contents of all catalogues of the GraspOS infrastructure. The UI is essentially the entry point to the infrastructure and it offers advanced search capabilities for the included resources supporting the retrieval based on a variety of criteria.

Value

The GraspOS architecture is designed with the aim to create an open ecosystem that not only supports evaluators in their job, but also facilitates the work of scholarly data managers and developers of tools and services which can be useful in research assessment. For instance, the architecture aims to facilitate the programmatic access of the supported data sources by the developers of monitoring tools and services and the curation of scholarly data sources by their managers leveraging the available enrichment tools and services. Finally, all GraspOS catalogues and registries are designed to be connected to the EOSC ecosystem.